

SUSTAINABLE STREETSAPES: ASSESSING PUBLIC PERCEPTION TOWARDS URBAN GREEN CORRIDORS AND PEDESTRIAN-FRIENDLY DESIGNS

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Paper Received On: 20 NOVEMBER 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 DECEMBER 2025

Published On: 01 JANUARY 2026

Abstract

Rapid urbanization has frequently put cars before people, which has resulted in worsening air quality, less walkability, and less livability in cities. As a result, in order to build healthier, people-centered communities, sustainable streetscapes that incorporate pedestrian walkways, green corridors, and non-motorized transportation are being implemented. This is a research that looks at how people view and interact with these kinds of urban projects. In addition to examining the impact of demographic characteristics on these impressions, the study attempts to gauge public awareness, contentment and acceptability of sustainable street features. In a few Indian cities that are putting green corridor projects into action, a mixed-method approach combining quantitative surveys (300 respondents) and qualitative field observations are considered. Descriptive statistics, correlation, regression, ANOVA, and factor analysis are important analytical tools for determining important public perception factors. Anticipated results include determining the factors that influence user satisfaction and propensity to embrace green mobility, such as accessibility, safety, aesthetic appeal, and environmental consciousness. In order to help planners and policymakers create inclusive, user-friendly, and environmentally sustainable urban environments, the study also suggests creating a Public Perception Index for Sustainable Streetscapes. In line with SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), the findings will support evidence-based urban design strategies that encourage public involvement and create resilient, habitable, and ecologically conscious cityscapes.

Keywords: *Sustainable Streetscapes, Public Perception, Green Corridors, Urban Design, Walkability etc.*

1. Introduction:

Urbanization has significantly reshaped cityscapes, often prioritizing vehicular movement over human-centered design. In light of growing challenges such as climate change, air pollution and declining livability, cities are increasingly adopting sustainable streetscapes urban spaces integrating green corridors, pedestrian walkways, cycling lanes and vegetation. These elements enhance aesthetics, mitigate heat islands, improve air quality and promote social interaction and active mobility.

Sustainable streetscapes emphasize walkability, accessibility, and ecological connectivity, with green corridors serving as vital ecological and social linkages that offer safe, comfortable and visually appealing routes. Despite national initiatives like the Smart City Mission and National Urban Transport Policy promoting green infrastructure, empirical research on public perception and user experience of such designs in India remains limited.

This study aims to assess public perception toward pedestrian-friendly street designs and urban green corridors, focusing on awareness, satisfaction and behavioral responses. The findings are expected to guide urban planners and policymakers in creating inclusive, resilient and sustainable streetscapes, contributing to Sustainable Development Goal 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities.

2. Review of Literature:

Sr. No.:	Name of the Author / Authors:	Year	Summarized Review:
1.	Tong Jia, Nor Zarifah Maliki, Tong Sen, Zheng Jiao	2025	Systematic PRISMA-based review of 46 studies highlighting walkability, accessibility, safety, and smart technologies as core elements of sustainable, pedestrian-friendly streetscapes.
2.	Fachrudin K. M. & Fachrudin K. M.	2025	Comparative study (Indonesia–Malaysia) highlighting green infrastructure, eco-pavements, and user-centered designs as vital for greener, resilient commercial streetscapes in Southeast Asia.
3.	Hilma Tamiami Fachrudin, Rahmi Karolina, Siti Hajar Misnan, Zhafira Rangkuti	2024	Analyzed Medan City's streetscapes; identified ecological and functional aspects—greenery, shaded sidewalks, and drainage—as key to comfort, safety, and sustainability in urban design.
4.	Fachrudin, Lubis, Putra, Karolina, Hassan & Shafwani	2024	Explored user preferences in Medan City; found that vegetation, open spaces, and well-designed furniture enhance comfort, walkability, and ecological sustainability in urban streetscapes.
5.	Ar. Kavya Kuldeep	2023	Studied Bengaluru's green corridors; found that sustainable streetscapes reduce heat, improve livability, and lessen urban environmental impact through greenery and climate-responsive design.
6.	Manika Goel, Amit Hajela, Safiullah Khan	2023	Reviewed effects of urban transit (elevated corridors) on greenery and pedestrian experience.

			Recommended integrating green corridors with transport design to balance mobility and ecology.
7.	Reeman Mohammed Rehan	2013	Emphasized sustainable streetscapes as tools for ecological balance and urban resilience. Advocated eco-friendly materials, renewable energy, and green infrastructure for livable cities.
8.	Ahsen Aleyna Çiçek		Compared Eskişehir (Turkey) and Jönköping (Sweden) to show how pedestrian-oriented, aesthetic street design enhances sustainability. Found that prioritizing walkability, green spaces, and accessibility fosters livable, inclusive cities.

Existing studies highlighted that sustainable streetscapes enhance walkability, livability, and environmental quality through green corridors, pedestrian comfort, and eco-friendly design. While global research provides strong theoretical and design frameworks, limited studies assess public perception, especially in developing cities. Hence, this study focuses on understanding how people perceive and interact with urban green corridors and pedestrian-friendly designs, aiming to support context-specific, inclusive and sustainable urban planning.

3. Research Methodology:

3.1 Research Objectives & Hypothesis:

Sr. No.:	Objectives:	Hypothesis:
1.	To examine the impact of awareness of green corridors on public perception towards sustainable and pedestrian-friendly street designs.	H0: There is no significant relationship between awareness of green corridors and public perception of sustainable street designs. H1: There is a significant positive relationship between awareness of green corridors and public perception of sustainable street designs.
2.	To compare public perceptions regarding the attractiveness and maintenance of green corridors and their support for city funding towards green corridor development.	H0: There is no significant difference between public perception of the attractiveness and maintenance of green corridors and their support for city funding toward these initiatives. H1: There is a significant difference between public perception of the attractiveness and maintenance of green corridors and their support for city funding toward these initiatives.
3.	To compare public perceptions of the aesthetic visual appeal of streets and their support for city funding towards green corridor development.	H0: There is no significant difference between public perception of the aesthetic visual appeal of streets and their level of support for city funding for green corridors. H1: There is a significant difference between public perception of the aesthetic visual appeal of streets and their level of support for city funding for green corridors.

4.	To examine the impact of the safety and accessibility of corridors from public transport stops on level of public satisfaction with accessibility features .	H0: There is no significant relationship between the safety and accessibility of corridors from public transport stops and satisfaction with accessibility features. H1: There is a significant positive relationship between the safety and accessibility of corridors from public transport stops and satisfaction with accessibility features.
5.	To compare public perceptions of the integration of vegetation and planters in corridors and the level of satisfaction with corridors that meet recreational and functional needs.	H0: There is no significant difference between public perception of vegetation integration in corridors and satisfaction with their suitability for recreational and daily walking needs. H1: There is a significant difference between public perception of vegetation integration and satisfaction with corridors' recreational and functional usability.

3.2 Research Design & Approach: Explanatory, cross-sectional and mixed-methods design (primarily quantitative with supportive qualitative observations.)

3.3 Study area & Population:

- **Study area:** Urban corridors / streets in Mumbai suburban city.
- **Target population:** Adult urban residents and regular users (≥ 18 years) who have visited / used the selected corridors in the past 6 months. Included commuters, shoppers, students and local residents.

3.4 Sampling strategy & size:

- **Sampling method:** Non-probability purposive and Snowball sampling for corridors of pedestrians through off-site surveys.
- **Sample size:** Targeted 315 responses.

3.5 Research Constructs:

- **Awareness (AW):** Knowledge of green corridors and sustainable street initiatives (scale mean of AW items).
- **Street Design Quality (SDQ):** Perceived continuity, surfacing, seating, layout, integration of vegetation.
- **Accessibility & Safety (AS):** Perceived pedestrian safety, lighting, accessibility features, separation from traffic.
- **Aesthetic Appeal (AA):** Perceived attractiveness and maintenance of landscaping and public art.
- **Public Perception (PP - Mediator):** Overall attitude toward corridors and perceived usefulness for city livability.
- **Satisfaction (ST):** User satisfaction with maintenance, comfort, and accessibility.

- **Willingness to Use / Support (WU):** Behavioral intention and support for funding/community participation.

3.6 Research Framework & Model:

3.7 Scope of the study:

- To support *evidence-based urban planning* for sustainability.
- To promote *citizen engagement* in city design initiatives.
- To aid in achieving *SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities)* and *National Urban Transport Policy* goals.
- To encourage cities to integrate green corridors and walkability as measurable performance indicators.

3.8 Limitations of the study:

- **Cross-sectional design:** The study employed a cross-sectional research design, where data was collected at a single point in time. This design allows for the identification of relationships between variables (e.g., awareness, perception, satisfaction) but cannot establish causal relationships.
- **Selection bias:** As the data was collected using non-probability (snowball and purposive) sampling through online platforms, there is a possibility of selection bias. Respondents who chose to participate may represent individuals who are more aware, interested or exposed to sustainable streetscapes, while non-visitors or less-engaged citizens might have responded based on limited prior experiences.

- **Self-report bias:** Since the data was collected through self-administered Google Forms, responses are subject to self-report bias. Some participants might have given socially desirable or idealized answers for instance, expressing stronger support for green initiatives or sustainability practices than they actually practice potentially affecting the objectivity of certain responses.
- **Seasonal / temporal effects:** The perception and use of green corridors and streetscapes can vary depending on seasonal and temporal factors such as weather, temperature, and time of year. Since data collection occurred within a specific period, respondents' satisfaction and perceptions might have been influenced by prevailing climatic or environmental conditions.

4. Data Analysis:

The reliability of data:

Statistics:	Value	Interpretation
k (Number of Items)	32	The scale has 32 questions being tested for reliability.
Sum of Item Variances	30.5001	Indicates the overall dispersion within each question.
Variance of Total Scores	291.1283	Reflects how much total test scores differ across respondents.
Cronbach's Alpha (α)	0.9241	Excellent internal consistency and reliability.

The reliability assessment of the 32-item scale produced a **Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.9241**, indicating **excellent internal consistency** among the measured items. This result implies that the items exhibit a high degree of interrelatedness and effectively measure a common underlying construct. The **sum of item variances (30.50)** and the **variance of total scores (291.13)** further confirm the stability and homogeneity of responses across the instrument. As per conventional psychometric standards, a Cronbach's Alpha value exceeding 0.90 denotes a highly reliable scale, although it may also reflect potential redundancy among some items. Overall, the findings substantiate that the instrument demonstrates **robust reliability and consistency**, making it suitable for advanced statistical analyses such as correlation and regression modeling.

Sr. No.:	Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Tests applied	Results
1.	Awareness Levels of Green Corridors	Public Perception towards Sustainable Street Designs	Regression Analysis	$\beta = 0.319$, $p < 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.15$, $R = 0.3869$

2.	Level of safety and accessibility of corridors from public transport stops	Level of public satisfaction with accessibility features	Regression Analysis	$\beta = 0.455$, $p < 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.118$, $R = 0.3436$
Sr. No.:	Variable 1	Variable 2	Tests applied	Results
3.	Attractiveness and Maintenance levels of Green Corridors	Level of Support to City Funding for Green Corridors	One way ANOVA	$p = 0.03139$ (< 0.05), $F = 4.65$
4.	Level of Aesthetic Visual Appeal along the Streets	Level of Support for City Funding for Green Corridors	One way ANOVA	$p = 0.04186$ (< 0.05), $F = 4.16$
5.	Integration of vegetation and planters in corridors	Level of satisfaction with corridors that meet recreational and functional needs	One way ANOVA	$p = 0.00406$ (< 0.05), $F = 8.32$

5. Conclusion & Findings:

Sr. No.:	Research Objectives	Findings / Results	Conclusion	Accepted Hypothesis
1.	To examine the impact of awareness of green corridors on public perception toward sustainable and pedestrian-friendly street designs.	Regression results show a significant positive relationship ($\beta = 0.319$, $p < 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.15$), indicating that awareness explains about 15% of the variance in perception.	Higher public awareness significantly enhances positive perceptions toward sustainable street designs and pedestrian-friendly environments.	H1
2.	To compare public perceptions regarding the attractiveness and maintenance of green corridors and their support for city funding toward green corridor development.	ANOVA result: $F = 4.65$, $p = 0.031$ (< 0.05), indicating a significant difference between the two perceptions.	Respondents show greater support for city funding compared to their satisfaction with the current attractiveness and maintenance of green corridors.	H1
3.	To compare public perceptions of the aesthetic visual appeal of streets and support for city funding for green corridor development.	ANOVA result: $F = 4.16$, $p = 0.042$ (< 0.05), confirming a statistically significant difference.	Respondents rated aesthetic appeal ($M = 3.97$) slightly higher than funding support ($M = 3.83$), showing higher appreciation for street	H1

			beauty than for financial contribution.	
4.	To examine the impact of the safety and accessibility of corridors from public transport stops on public satisfaction with accessibility features.	Regression result: $\beta = 0.455$, $F = 41.76$, $p < 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.118$ - a strong, significant positive impact of safety and accessibility on satisfaction.	Improved corridor safety and accessibility substantially increase satisfaction, emphasizing the need for inclusive, well-connected urban design.	H1
5.	To compare public perceptions of the integration of vegetation and planters in corridors and their satisfaction with recreational and functional usability.	ANOVA result: $F = 8.32$, $p = 0.004$ (< 0.05), indicating a significant difference between the two perceptions.	Respondents were more satisfied with the recreational usability of corridors ($M = 3.09$) than with vegetation integration ($M = 2.86$), highlighting functional preference over aesthetic planting.	H1

6. Suggestions & Recommendations:

Area emphasized on:	Findings / Insights	Recommendations
1. Enhancing Awareness and Community Engagement	Higher awareness of green corridors significantly improves public perception ($\beta = 0.319$, $p < 0.001$).	Urban authorities should launch awareness and education campaigns highlighting environmental, social, and health benefits of green corridors. Encourage community participation through workshops, street fairs, and digital platforms to strengthen ownership toward sustainable initiatives.
2. Improving Attractiveness and Maintenance of Green Corridors	Respondents showed greater support for city funding ($M = 3.91$) than satisfaction with attractiveness and maintenance ($M = 3.74$).	Upgrade visual quality and upkeep of corridors through regular maintenance, native plant landscaping, seasonal planting, and artistic street furniture to enhance aesthetics and satisfaction.

3. Integrating Aesthetics and Functional Street Designs	Aesthetic visual appeal (M = 3.97) rated higher than support for city funding (M = 3.83), showing appreciation for design but limited civic participation.	Blend visual identity with usability by ensuring that streets are both beautiful and functional through shaded walkways, accessible sidewalks, and eco-friendly materials.
4. Prioritizing Safety and Accessibility	Strong positive relationship between safety / accessibility and satisfaction ($\beta = 0.455, p < 0.001$).	Improve pedestrian safety and connectivity by integrating barrier-free designs, clear pedestrian crossings, adequate lighting, and direct links to public transport to ensure inclusive corridors.
5. Balancing Green Integration with Recreational Usability	Higher satisfaction with recreational usability (M = 3.09) than with vegetation integration (M = 2.86) ($F = 8.32, p = 0.004$).	Strategically place greenery to enhance functionality without obstructing movement. Adopt multi-use green corridors combining vegetation, shaded walkways, and social or leisure spaces.
6. Strengthening Policy and Funding Frameworks	Need for integrated urban sustainability strategies and stronger financial support for corridor maintenance.	Establish a dedicated urban green infrastructure policy with design standards, maintenance protocols, and community stewardship models. Encourage PPPs and participatory budgeting for sustainable corridor development.
7. Monitoring, Evaluating and Scaling Successful Models	Continuous evaluation is essential to ensure performance and replicability of green corridor designs.	Introduce impact assessment frameworks to monitor accessibility, comfort, safety, and satisfaction. Use data-driven feedback loops to refine designs and scale successful models citywide.
General Recommendations	A holistic, people-centered approach combining awareness, accessibility, aesthetics and participation is the key.	Green corridors should be developed as inclusive, sustainable, and resilient urban spaces that balance environmental, social, and functional goals.

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